

The Crucial Role of BioImage Analysts in Scientific Research and Publication

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Abstract

Bioimage analysis (BIA) is a critical discipline in the field of biological research. It overcomes the limitations of subjective analysis in microscopy through the creation of quantitative and reproducible methods. This paper is the result of a recent meeting of bioimage analysts who aimed to summarize the current state of affairs for BIA including categorizing current obstacles and offering possible solutions to them.

We believe that the establishment of dedicated BIA support in academic institutions is crucial to improving the quality and efficiency of research and has the potential to significantly advance scientific discovery and innovation. However, this potential cannot be fully realized as long as the field faces challenges such as lack of training, limited career paths, insufficient credit and recognition of contributions to research outcomes.

We propose strategies to overcome these barriers and bring about a cultural shift in recognising the value of BIA, such as standardizing tools, improving training and recognition. We also ask for improved funding, standardized practices, and enhanced collaboration within the scientific community concluding with a call to action for all stakeholders to join efforts in advancing BIA.

Introduction

Bioimage analysis as an emerging discipline

Computational analysis of light microscopy images is a comparatively recent development in the centuries-long history of microscopy for biological discovery. Earlier, scientists had relied on the human visual system - an intricate neural network evolved over several million years, but ultimately not a recipe for reproducible quantification (Jambor, 2023). The subjective nature of such analyses has been famously played out in neuroscience, where Golgi and Cajal used the same method to reach widely different conclusions; and it is perhaps best seen in pathology, where the practice of discerning phenotypes from images has long been possible but where many studies evaluate cases of poor agreement between individuals (e.g. (Elmore et al., 2017; Hamilton et al., 2015; Polley et al., 2013; Varga et al., 2012). Such disagreement, alongside limitations of human perception in detecting subtle phenotypes (Gibson et al., 2015), underlies the critical need for quantitative, reproducible methods in bioimage analysis (BIA). Unfortunately, fear of the unknown and misconceptions regarding the reliability and usefulness of BIA have helped contribute to its delayed adoption.

Even where there is agreement on the need for quantitative BIA methods, the sheer number of advanced microscopy techniques further complicates the landscape. Microscopes are both ubiquitous and extraordinarily heterogeneous. This combination means that microscopy possesses a low barrier to entry but faces a significant challenge in method standardization, requiring an entire career track of experts who fully understand and can help optimize these

experiments - that of the Imaging Scientist (Wright et al., 2024). This heterogeneity persists into the imaging data itself, explaining the extensive time and expertise required to design and implement robust BIA methods. While artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) can and will continue to dramatically improve the throughput of BIA and open up newer, easier-to-use analytical options, human expertise will still be required for the foreseeable future in order to provide the detailed understanding necessary to apply these techniques effectively.

We therefore stand at a critical juncture where the establishment of dedicated BIA support within academic/research institutions, in the form of expert groups, facilities, and dedicated staff in individual laboratories, presents a huge opportunity to enhance the quality and efficacy of research output (Figure 1). BIA experts not only offer direct contributions that lead to better data utilization, more principled and conclusive results, and stronger publications, but also foster a highly productive environment conducive to fewer revision cycles and improved project setups, directly impacting scientific endeavors (Jambor et al., 2021; Jonkman et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2024; Senft et al., 2023; Soltwedel and Haase, 2023). Since what can be concluded from an experiment ultimately rests on its experimental design, inclusion of BIA experts during the experimental design phase can be the difference between a successful and an unsuccessful outcome; per Ronald Fisher's quip "To consult the statistician after an experiment is finished is often merely to ask him to conduct a *post-mortem* examination. He can perhaps say what the experiment died of". Bioimage analysts thus play a pivotal role in elevating an institution's scientific recognition and reputation, thereby attracting superior talents and nurturing a vibrant scientific community that propels forward the frontiers of science.

As we peer into the future of BIA, it is evident that the field is technologically poised for a paradigm shift. As ML approaches increasingly automate more routine tasks such as segmentation, future BIA specialists will increasingly be free to focus on experimental design and the development of more sophisticated methods. Culturally, however, this evolution will require a shift towards a more inclusive, collaborative approach, where bioimage analysts are integral to the experimental design process from the outset. If a concerted effort is made to foster a culture that recognizes the intrinsic value of quantitative BIA (whether performed by individual researchers or by analysis specialists) and the indispensable role of analysts in advancing scientific discovery, deeper scientific insights and more efficient research methodologies are only a few of the possible positive returns. Here we describe the results of a recent meeting of bioimage analysts (comprising BIA tool users, tool developers, and method developers) in which we attempted to categorize the current obstacles and possible solutions to the creation of such a new BIA culture.

Main Text

What factors inhibit wider adoption of bioimage analysis?

Educating researchers about the possibilities and requirements of bioimage analysis

In addition to the cultural barriers described above, several other factors limit the ability of researchers to perform high-end and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) (Barker et al., 2022; Kemmer et al., 2023; Wilkinson et al., 2016) BIA in biology. Researchers wishing to begin quantitatively analyzing their bioimaging data but without BIA education or support may not be sure which tools to begin with in the limited time they can allot to analyzing image data. The lack of documentation and proper training materials for BIA tools further discourages researchers from delving deeper. Once biologists begin their analyses, technological challenges, such as insufficient computing power, storage space, or funding for commercial licenses are real obstacles. The help of a BIA expert with advanced knowledge and access to more powerful hardware and/or software is therefore often critical to a researcher's success.

Effective BIA requires a comprehensive understanding of several diverse fields, including understanding of image processing, creation of complex workflows (Cimini, 2024; Miura and Nørrelykke, 2021), and increasingly, familiarity with deep learning (Figure 1). At each step, choice between algorithms and/or setting of large complex parameter sets may be required. The increasing computational demands of BIA highlight the need to provide biologists with programming training opportunities, empowering them with the skills to address complex biological questions more effectively. This technical understanding must be paired with thorough understanding of experimental design, including what types of artifacts are likely under various sample preparations and/or imaging conditions and how best to ameliorate them (Culley et al., 2023; Senft et al., 2023). Statistical considerations also abound: what data should be used to train or validate an algorithm? Which metrics should be calculated and how should they be aggregated? How should variability and uncertainty be assessed? How should the results be reported so that they are reproducible and interpretable? Only with all of these aspects in place can bioimage data be accurately analyzed, underlining the importance of developing experts that researchers can consult with throughout the experimental design and execution process.

Lack of career paths and support for bioimage analysts

The broad technical knowledge required to successfully perform BIA typically takes many years to develop, especially in the absence of many formalized pathways for learning its various disparate aspects. As such, one common and logical structure is to treat bioimage analysts like other technical specialists (such as bioinformaticians and imaging scientists) and have their skills and expertise available through academic core facilities. To succeed in such roles,

bioimage analysts must possess not only the technical skills described but also the ability to communicate and train researchers, and to understand analysis techniques to advise on the requirements and resources for data sharing (Figure 1). Often, since they have the greatest exposure to user difficulties as well as broad kinds of biological problems and broad subsets of the tool ecosystem, such BIA application experts also serve a critical role by communicating with (or even serving as) the research software engineers creating BIA tools about the unmet needs of the community.

Few people currently have all the skills needed to succeed in this career and those who do find the academic facilities career path to be challenging and unstable. While in some regions, such as parts of Europe, it is common to find regional or national funding for facilities staff (O'Toole and Marrison, 2023; Pfander et al., 2022), in other regions such as the United States, national funding for core facilities staff is difficult if not impossible to acquire, leaving funding to individual institutions. According to a recent GloBIAS survey of the field (personal communication), of 166 bioimage analysts working in facilities, fewer than 20% reported that their facility was >75% internally funded, suggesting most institutions do not have sufficient funding dedicated for BioImage Analysts to cover salary and expenses. Most analysts rely on a combination of collaborator's grants and microscope usage fees to make up the budget, with a smaller fraction of money coming from their own grants, external consulting, or fees from analysis projects. Only 1 respondent reported being able to fund at least 75% of their position on image analysis fees alone, likely reflecting similar problems in other kinds of computational core facilities to cost recover (due to higher salaries of computational experts and lower willingness of researchers to pay for computational work)(Dragon et al., 2020). Without reliable funding from the institution or a grant agency, academic facility bioimage analysts typically have little job security and low pay, and face the same difficulties in career progression found in other core facility careers (Adami et al., 2021; Dragon et al., 2020; Lippens et al., 2022; Rahmoon et al., 2024; Soltwedel and Haase, 2023; Tranfield and Lippens, 2024; Waithe, 2021; Wright et al., 2024).

Unfortunately, the historical reliance on qualitative assessment in biology research has led to relative under-development and under-appreciation of the difficulty of BIA, which can combine with other cultural biases against facility technical specialists(Knudtson et al., 2019; Kos-Braun et al., 2020) (Figure 2). If researchers approach image analysts at all, they may approach them with predetermined mindsets about what an analysis "should" look like and what the results must be, rather than engaging in a collaborative dialogue to explore the full spectrum of analytical tools available. This disconnect not only suppresses innovation in novel methods and approaches but also prevents the optimal application of BIA in addressing complex scientific questions. In many scientific environments bioimage analysts find their contributions condensed to brief mentions in the methods section or relegated to supplementary materials, despite their pivotal role in shaping the research outcome from the outset. This oversight not only diminishes the value of their expertise but also risks the integrity and reproducibility of scientific findings. The combination of low pay and less acknowledgement can lead to burnout in such analysts, who often find themselves both better respected and better compensated in industry roles. This

leads to a "brain drain" where highly talented experts who serve as a critical resource for both researchers and BIA tool creators are often lost from the academic community.

Misaligned incentive structures lead to moving fast and making things

The BIA experts who develop new software tools, much like their colleagues who focus on working with researchers on BIA application, often find themselves succeeding in spite of current structures rather than because of them. Such developers need working conditions that will inspire them to develop, maintain and update those tools, including a "critical mass" of local experts to interact with. Unfortunately, the current incentive structure in academic research makes it harder than necessary for people to build and support the practical BIA tools that the wider community needs (Figure 3).

One of the main quantified outputs of academic research is peer-reviewed publications (Derrick, G.E., Hettrick, S., Baker, J., Karoune, E., Kerridge, S., Fletcher, G., Chue Hong, N., Ballantyne, L., Fransmann, J., Roche, T., 2024). The "publish-or-perish" paradigm encourages researchers to focus on their own area of expertise rather than target their tools broadly. BIA tool developers are expected to continually publish novel methods that demonstrably improve on the state-of-the-art according to some benchmark – even though novelty and benchmark performance are not reliable surrogate measures of usefulness in the real world (Maier-Hein et al., 2018) and a 'proof-of-concept' algorithm that works on a restricted dataset may be publishable, often even without providing any code to enable scrutiny or reproducibility (Sharma et al., 2023). Academic research incentive structures favor novelty over the refinement or integration of existing solutions, and academic research labs are typically primarily staffed by short-term trainees who are unlikely to continue maintaining software created in previous positions. Current structures are therefore creating a "tool graveyard" of unmaintained, standalone software developed for a particular project, rather than reusable workflows or plugins for existing BIA tools (Deschamps et al., 2023; Moses and Pachter, 2022).

Making an algorithm accessible to researchers can be a double edged sword for tool developers: a BIA specialist that takes the considerable time and effort needed to package their algorithm as a new piece of well-documented, user-friendly, and open-source software will inevitably end up with fewer publications, a false perception of lower productivity, and their work being dismissed as 'software, not research'. If instead one attempts to incorporate one's algorithm into a larger tool within the ecosystem, it may be falsely perceived as only a trivial advance even where the functionality is fully novel. The payoff from such efforts is also unclear: even where software is broadly used by non-computational users, use does not guarantee a commensurate level of citation (Giving software its due, 2019). The amount of overlap and redundancy in these tools serves not only to dilute the community's resources but can also have a considerable environmental impact due to the computational resources required to retrain deep learning models for slight advancements. Together, these factors actively promote the continual reinvention of BIA methods that are 'usable enough' and 'good enough' to publish in individual studies, but not capable of addressing the wider needs of the community in a truly FAIR way.

Pathways to improved adoption and integration of bioimage analysis

Despite the challenges described above, as a community of professionals we are hopeful about the future of BIA. By streamlining our efforts, working for improved recognition and better-aligned incentives, and improving access to BIA, we believe the culture can be changed for the better. This will require a community effort, but one we are confident will pay substantial dividends.

Creation of field best practices and coalescence around standardized tools and approaches

One effort which can be led by the BIA community itself is to develop better standards and harmonized approaches, simplifying the process of learning BIA and making it easier to train future analysts and researchers. Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort across the BIA community, including researchers, developers, funders, and policy makers. Fostering interoperability through common file formats (Hiner et al., 2016; Moore et al., 2021), the creation and adoption of metadata formats which include aspects of experimental design, and promoting software engineering best practices for greater modularity and documentation (Afiaz et al., 2023; Sharma et al., 2023; Sivagurunathan et al., 2023; Wiesmann et al., 2015) will ensure that data can be used and re-used by many tools. The establishment of standardized datasets and metrics for tool evaluation (Biaflows; Maier-Hein et al., 2024) and the benchmarking initiatives these enable (such as setting up challenges and leaderboards for biological problems (Caicedo et al., 2019; Ma et al., 2023; Maška et al., 2023; Ulman et al., 2017)), can enhance visibility and comparability among tools and reduce duplication. Moreover, engaging with policy makers and funders to emphasize the importance of software maintenance, upgradeability, and usability in grant funding can de-incentivize the creation of single-use code and incentivize the creation of tools that are not only innovative but also sustainable and accessible. By adopting these strategies, the BIA community can mitigate the issues stemming from the proliferation of tools, fostering a more integrated, efficient, and collaborative research environment.

The creation of field best practices will also improve BIA education. Bioimage analysts are typically on the front line of such efforts, and a crucial aspect of this educational role involves creating FAIR training materials that not only facilitate learning but also promote the sharing and standardization of best practices within the community (Haase et al., 2024; Imreh et al., 2023). The creation of standardized, modularized educational materials that bioimage analysts can improve and access will improve all analysts' ability to effectively train diverse audiences with tailored curricula, from novices to advanced practitioners, in both formal educational settings and more informal workshops.

Improved recognition and training for bioimage analysis as a career path

While simplifying and standardizing tools and methods represents a critical first step to improved adoption of BIA, the establishment of a career path for dedicated BIA specialists is still vital. BIA experts (alongside their Imaging Scientist colleagues) represent a critical stable source of knowledge and expertise within their local bioimaging community. Making it easier to increase the number of BIA experts in our community, both by expanding existing training efforts (Cimini et al., 2024; Martins et al., 2021) and promoting better career paths and acknowledgement structures will be essential to generating the expertise needed to push current imaging science forward.

As BIA becomes a career path, it can follow the lead of other kinds of core facilities in promoting career levels, as well as adopting and promoting training standards and programs (Adami et al., 2021; Cimini et al., 2024; Waters, 2020; Wright et al., 2024). At present, recognition of academic achievements is largely driven by peer-reviewed publications, which favors creation of new tools over maintenance of existing tools. The proliferation of dataset, methods, and software sections in journals is a welcome development in this direction. Alternative mechanisms of recognition can also be promoted, such as the increased use of narrative CVs, which emphasize the value of collaboration and support work, as well as the creation of awards which allow hiring and promotion committees to recognize excellence and community value. The BIA community could work to create awards to recognize the diverse contributions of its members (from enthusiastic students to seasoned Principal Investigators), which would foster recognition of innovation, collaboration, and excellence. Creation and adoption of a more comprehensive awards system to highlight the impactful work across all levels of scientific engagement could be administered by reputable entities within the community, such as GloBIAS, funders like CZI, or existing institutes/universities.

Better alignment of incentive structures to promote bioimage analysis

While intra-community validation is critical, quantifying the benefits and contributions of BIA in measurable terms poses a challenge, as each institution or granting agency will value Key Performance Indicators such as higher impact factor, accelerated publication timeline, or production of open data differently. Within universities, academic stakeholders must recognize the value of having one or several BIA experts on site, who can train users and propose tailored solutions, in contrast with purchasing proprietary software with limited scope and user training. The creation of dedicated BIA core facilities and/or the embedding of bioimage analysts in bioimaging core facilities can help centralize and share costs for these services which are crucial for the functioning of the department (or whole university). In accordance with common funding models in both imaging core facilities and bioinformatics facilities (Dragon et al., 2020; O'Toole and Marrison, 2023; Soltwedel and Haase, 2023; Tranfield and Lippens, 2024; Waithe, 2021), bioimage analysts can of course generate revenue but also not need to be fully cost recovered by any user fees. It is also important to consider evaluating their productivity on facility metrics rather than mere "papers published". Here, we provide a draft template (Authors of the paper "The Crucial Role of BioImage Analysts in Scientific Research and Publication") (Supplemental Data 1) to help bioimage analysts (or those wishing to employ them) to translate their varied endeavors into monetary value. While it must be personalized for every situation,

this can be used as part of a discussion on key performance indicators with institutional or government leaders to explain the value of a BIA facility(Soltwedel and Haase, 2023) .

When it comes to the creation and maintenance of BIA tools, the continued development of BIA tools and the training of researchers to use them is dependent on the recognition and funding of these efforts. Assessing the impact of bioimage analysts is a necessary step to allow them to receive relevant funding. Whereas most current government funding focuses heavily on novelty, the BIA field would strongly benefit from funding dedicated to software maintenance and documentation, which are essential to users; while some philanthropic funders, such as CZI, have such calls, far more funding is needed globally. Developing this type of funding would promote the long-term maintenance and support of existing solutions, rather than the recurrent cycle of software development and abandonment. Such a shift in the funding model would be accompanied by the existing community effort to define criteria for quality software and good practices for software development and maintenance. Taken as a whole, these measures could help direct efforts towards a smaller number of tools, with the benefits of greatly improved quality, accessibility and usability.

Improving access and understanding within the broader biology community

Securing increased funding and recognition will be made vastly easier if the broader biology community becomes more actively engaged in using BIA tools and approaches on their own data. The first step to improve training of BIA researchers is to understand the necessary skill set summarized above. To complement, existing material should be reviewed (such as surveys and meta analyses of (Jamali et al., 2022; Miura, 2021; Schmidt et al., 2022; Sivagurunathan et al., 2023; Waithe, 2021)) and cataloged. Existing training material should be expanded on missing items, such as

- courses on the application of machine learning techniques in BIA, focusing on how they can be used for more efficient and accurate image processing and analysis,
- training on ethical considerations, data privacy, and the responsible use of bioimage data, especially in contexts where sensitive or personal information may be involved,
- training on the importance of performing validations correctly and on how to report and interpret results,
- training on proper statistics, such as informing about p-hacking and issues of reporting p-values,
- training on research data management(Sarkans et al., 2021; Schmidt et al., 2022; Schmidt et al., 2024) by developing a concept for data management plan consulting specifically for BIA, which must contain sections about who is responsible for processing the data, where they get their resources (human resources, storage resources, and computing resources) from, and how to FAIRfy the project (sharing data and code).

Based on this, new training schools and curricula should be defined and planned, as well as community efforts (including funding acquisition) for training schools in which one can "train the trainers". Importantly, training materials have to be made accessible to a diverse audience, ideally understandable for researchers with various backgrounds, including adjustments for individuals with disabilities, and translations into multiple languages to reach a global audience.

Creating a variety of kinds of materials (ranging from informal blog posts and videos to full academic courses) will be critical for wider adoption.

For future assistance, reviewing and potentially defining new reporting guidelines for BIA-specific topics helps researchers on how to structure and report their studies. In addition, compiling a collection of case studies that illustrate the practical application of BIA skills in various research contexts can serve as a valuable resource for both learners and trainers.

A culture shift around the importance of bioimage analysis

A central aspect of our strategy is cultivating a culture that values and understands the importance of BIA, thereby securing buy-in from all our various stakeholders (Figure 4):

1. **Enhancing visibility:** Actively participating in scientific conferences and forums not only boosts the visibility of BIA but also facilitates the exchange of ideas and foster collaborations.
2. **Building empathy and collaboration:** be willing to learn from the other and give them the means to learn from us. Developing a common language is key. Engaging in activities like rescue sessions for problematic datasets and pair programming can bridge the gap between bioimage analysts and researchers.
3. **Highlighting unique contributions:** By presenting case studies and research outcomes that were made possible exclusively through advanced BIA, we underscore the unique value that our field brings to scientific discovery. These success stories can serve as powerful testimonials to the critical role of quantitative analysis.
4. **Advocating for standards in publishing:** Lobbying for journals to mandate not just the inclusion of quantitative analysis but also a thorough description of the methodologies employed and encouraging image analysts to conceptualize methodologies as standalone publications are important to elevate the recognition of BIA work. Journals could include publication checklists (Schmied et al., 2024) to ensure that all image quantification is performed according to field standards, similar to what many do for statistical analysis.
5. **Securing support from funders:** Pushing for funding bodies to recognize and support the infrastructure of the BIA community, including the development of communal resources and spaces for collaboration, is crucial.
6. **Emphasizing the importance of user support:** Advocating for the integration of user support as a fundamental component of software development and maintenance funding ensures that tools are not only technically robust but also user-friendly and widely adopted.

Conclusions and Outlook

In reflecting on the current state and future trajectory of BIA within the broader scientific community, it is evident that while significant steps have been taken, a multitude of challenges still lie ahead. The complexity and diversity of biological data, coupled with the rapid evolution of imaging technologies, necessitate a concerted effort to unlock the full potential of BIA for advancing scientific knowledge. The path forward is not the responsibility of a single entity but requires the collaborative engagement of all stakeholders involved in the bioimaging ecosystem. This includes but is not limited to, researchers, bioinformaticians, software developers, policy makers, and funding agencies. A synergistic approach, combining both top-down strategies from organizational and policy perspectives and bottom-up initiatives driven by community-based innovations, is paramount for fostering an environment conducive to solving the complex problem at hand.

Despite these challenges, the BIA community is currently best characterized as motivated by a shared sense of organization and purpose. The enthusiasm and readiness to contribute to the collective mission of enhancing the rigor, reproducibility, and impact of scientific research through advanced BIA are palpable. Workshops such as the 'Effectively Communicating Bioimage Analysis' meeting which led to this paper play a crucial role in stimulating this community, equipping participants with the knowledge, skills, and networks necessary to advocate for and implement best practices in BIA.

As we look to the future, it is imperative that we continue to nurture this collaborative spirit, fostering open dialogue, knowledge exchange, and innovation. By doing so, we can collectively surmount the challenges that lie ahead, paving the way for groundbreaking discoveries that will propel the field of biomedical research forward. In this spirit of unity and determination, we extend an open invitation to all stakeholders to join us in this endeavor. Together, we are poised to make a substantial impact on the advancement of science, underpinned by the power of effective BIA.

In conclusion, the journey ahead is undeniably challenging, yet filled with immense potential. Armed with a clear vision, a robust framework for collaboration, and a relentless drive for excellence, the BIA community is well-equipped to embrace the complexities of the future. Let us proceed with confidence and collective resolve, committed to the pursuit of scientific innovation and the advancement of human health.

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Figures

Figure 1

Figure 1: Overview of the key skills and capabilities of a Bioimage Analysis, BIA, specialist.

Figure 2

Figure 2: A concise etiquette guide for interacting with BIA specialists.

Figure 3

Barriers to Bioimage Analysis

Figure 3: Barriers to effective uptake of BIA.

Figure 4

Figure 4: A vision for the BIA community going forward.

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